

Vanadium, Part XVII; Oxo-Vanadium(IV) Mixed Chelates with Tridentate Dibasic Schiff bases and Bidentate α - α' -Dipyridyl (or -Phenanthroline)

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Oxo-vanadium(IV) mixed chelates having one tridentate dibasic Schiff base anion and another neutral, strong field ligand α - α' -dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) have been prepared. The quadrivalence of vanadium is established by their paramagnetic moments, by characteristic vanadyl stretch and d-d ligand field bands. The complexes exhibit similar spectral behaviour in solid state, in donor solvent, as also in non-donor solvent. A six-coordinate stereochemistry is proposed on the basis of available evidences.

Some oxo-vanadium(IV) mixed chelates with tridentate monobasic Schiff bases and bidentate monobasic hydroxyaldehydes are known¹. These syntheses were not deliberately designed, instead arose out of attempts to prepare homochelates. Extending our interest on Schiff base complexes of oxo-vanadium(IV)², we now report a group of oxo-vanadium(IV) mixed chelates having one tridentate dibasic Schiff base anion and another neutral, strong field ligand like α - α' -dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline). The Schiff bases employed are of N-salicylidene amino acid types, being the products of interaction of an aldehyde (salicylaldehyde or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde) with an amino acid (glycine, alanine, anthranilic acid) or *o*-aminophenol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the mixed chelates: Ethanol solution of the hydroxyaldehyde (0.01 mole) was refluxed with the amino acid (0.01 mole) in ethanol for 30–45 mins on a steam bath. Syrupy vanadyl chloride (0.01 mole) in ethanol was treated with sodium acetate (0.02 mole) (also in ethanol) and filtered. The filtrate was added to the above Schiff base solution and refluxing continued for about 30–45 mins.

α - α' -Dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) (0.01 mole) was next added and refluxing continued for one hour. The product, often brownish red or yellow, separated out from the solution. Sometimes it was necessary to distil off some solvent and to cool in the refrigerator overnight to yield shining crystals. In some cases, however, water was added to initiate precipitation. All samples were dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

The compounds are usually soluble in chloroform and pyridine but less so in methanol, ethanol, benzene and ether.

The characterization data of the complexes appear in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Characterization data of oxo-vanadium(IV) mixed chelates

Complex	Colour	Analysis*		Magnetic moment, BM, ($^{\circ}$ K)
		% V Found	% N Found	
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Salgly)]2H ₂ O	Orange	10.86(11.08)	8.80(9.13)	1.76(295)
[VO(dipy)(Salgly)]	Brown	12.30(12.75)	10.20(10.50)	1.75(302)
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Salan)]0.5H ₂ O	Brown	10.08(10.30)	8.61(8.48)	1.71(310)
[VO(dipy)(Salan)]	Brown	10.64(11.03)	8.90(9.08)	1.62(307)
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Salalan)]0.5H ₂ O	Brown	11.31(11.40)	9.06(9.39)	1.58(300)
[VO(dopy)(Salalan)]	Black brown	11.98(12.31)	10.28(10.14)	1.54(309)
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Salam)]	Black brown	10.88(11.13)	8.95(9.17)	1.68(297)
[VO(dipy)(Salam)]	Brown	11.60(11.75)	9.90(9.67)	1.62(310)
[VO(<i>o</i> -pen)(Hynapgly)]0.5H ₂ O	Red	10.53(10.55)	8.90(8.69)	1.76(308)
[VO(dipy)(Hynapgly)]0.5H ₂ O	Red	11.10(11.11)	9.70(9.15)	1.68(296)
[VO(<i>o</i> -pen)(Hynapalan)]1.5H ₂ O	Yellow	10.08(9.90)	7.98(8.15)	1.80(301)
[VO(dipy)(Hynapalan)]1.5H ₂ O	Yellow	10.70(10.38)	8.37(8.55)	1.85(308)
[VO(dipy)(Hynapan)]	Yellow	10.08(9.96)	8.20(8.20)	1.82(295)

* The figures in parentheses are the calculated values.

Abbreviations : SalglyH₂ = Salicylaldehyde glycine Schiff base; SalanH₂ = Salicylaldehyde anthranilic acid Schiff base; SalalanH₂ = Salicylaldehyde alanine Schiff base; SalamH₂ = Salicylaldehyde aminophenol Schiff base; HynapglyH₂ = 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde glycine Schiff base; HynapalanH₂ = 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde alanine Schiff base; HynapanH₂ = 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde anthranilic acid Schiff base; dipy = α - α' -dipyridyl; *o*-phen = *o*-phenanthroline.

Analyses : Vanadium was estimated as V₂O₅ after igniting the compounds to constant weight. Nitrogen was determined by semi-micro Duma combustion.

Magnetic measurements : Magnetic susceptibility was determined in a Gouy balance using G.R. copper sulphate pentahydrate (E.Merck) as calibrant. Magnetic moment was calculated as usual with diamagnetic corrections obtained from Pascal's constants³. The magnetic moments are given in Table 1.

Infrared spectra : The IR spectra of the samples were run in KBr pellets with the aid of Perkin Elmer Infracord. Some band assignments are given in Table 2.

Electronic spectra : Absorption spectra were recorded in a Hilger-Watts UVISPEK Spectrophotometer using 1 cm cell. Solvents used were of analar grade. Mull spectra (liquid paraffin) of the solid complexes were measured in the same spectrophotometer adopting the procedure of Lee *et al.*⁴. The spectral data of some representative complexes are given in Table 3.

TABLE 2

Probable assignments of some of the main infrared bands (in cm⁻¹)

(A)

Dipy ^a	[MoO ₂ Cl.dipy]	[VO(dipy)SO ₄]	[VO(dipy) (Hynapan)]	[VO(dipy) (Salam)]	Assignment
	952	971 m vb,sh	962 vs	962 s	M = O stretch
760	775 s	769 s	775 m	763 s	
1320	1321 s	1316 s	1325 m	1316 m,sh	Dipyridyl bands
1425		1439 vs	1429 m	1439 s	
1590	1601 s	1600 s,sh	1600 s	1613 vs,sh	Dipyridyl band
	1609 m,sh		1613 m		C = N stretch
			1635 s		COO-stretch

^aP. C. H. Mitchell, *J. Inorg Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 963.

(B)

<i>o</i> -phen ^b	[Mo ₂ O ₄ Cl ₂ - <i>o</i> -phen ₂] H ₂ O ^b	[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)SO ₄]	[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Hynapgly)]	Assignment
625	641 722	645 m,b	649 w	<i>o</i> -phen bands
853	851	855 m,b,sh	855 s	
885	872	877 m	877 m	
	961	~ 980 m,b,sh	957	M = O stretch
		1627 s	1600 s	<i>o</i> -phen bands,
			1613 s	C = N stretch
			1640 s	COO-stretch

s = strong ; m = medium ; w = weak ; b = broad ; sh = shoulder.

^bP. A. Marzilli and D. A. Buckingham, *Austral J. Chem.*, 1966, **19**, 2259.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All the complexes are coloured and quite stable. The quadrivalence of vanadium is established by their paramagnetic moments, by characteristic vanadyl stretch and d-d ligand field bands. The magnetic moments (Table 1) of most of the complexes are in the region of spin-only value expected for a d¹ system. The near-normal values show insignificant interaction between neighbouring vanadium ions.

The probable assignments of some of the main infrared spectral bands are given in Table 2. The infra red spectra of [VO(*o*-phen)SO₄] and [VO(dipy)SO₄] have been studied for comparison. Some bands of [MoO₂Cl.dipy]⁵ and [Mo₂O₄Cl₂(*o*-phen)₂]⁶ are also included in Table 2 for the purpose of assignment.

TABLE 3

*Electronic spectral data of some of the oxo-vanadium(IV) mixed chelates**

Complex	State	Absorption max. kK	$(\epsilon_{molar}$ for solution)	
[VO(dipy)(Hynapan)]	A	21.28 CT;	16.95;	13.42 vb
	B		16.95 (230)	13.33 (46) vb
	C		16.95 (144)	13.33 (42) vb
[VO(dipy)(Salan)]	A	23.25 CT;		13.51 b
	B		~ 18.18 (200) sh;	13.16 (25) vb
	C		~ 18.18 (109) sh;	13.16 (18) vb
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Salgly)]2H ₂ O	A	25.00 CT; ~ 20.82 CT,sh;		13.88 vb
	B			13.79 (35) vb
	C			13.79 (32) vb
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Salalan)]	A	25.00 CT; ~ 22.22 CT,sh;		13.88 b
	B			13.79 (26) vb
	C			13.79 (28) vb

Abbreviations : A = mull spectra; B = chloroform spectra; C = pyridine spectra; CT = charge transfer; vb = very broad; b = broad; sh = shoulder.

* Although the spectra of all the complexes were studied in different states, only a few are included in this table.

(a) *Metal-oxygen stretching frequencies* : The presence of monomeric VO unit is revealed by the infra-red spectral data (Table 2) showing the vanadyl stretch ($960 \pm 14 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). A strong band in this region is expected for all compounds containing a metal oxygen double bond⁷.

(b) *α - α' -dipyridyl (*o*-phenanthroline) frequencies* : The α - α' -dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) bands in the mixed chelates are compared with known complexes like [MoO₂Cl.dipy]⁸ and [Mo₂O₄Cl₂(*o*-phen)₂]⁶. This comparison shows some slight shifts in band positions indicating coordination of α - α' -dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline to the metal ion (Table 2).

(c) *Co-ordinated carboxyl band* : On coordination, there is a lowering of the carboxyl stretch from ~ 1700 – 1725 cm^{-1} to $\sim 1640 \text{ cm}^{-1,8,9}$. This assignment of $\sim 1640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ band to carboxyl stretch in the present series of complexes is justified since the complexes containing the salicylaldehyde-*o*-aminophenol Schiff base do not show this band.

(d) *Coordinated imine group* : Usual stretching frequency for the coordinated C = N group lies in the region 1600 – $1630 \text{ cm}^{-1,1,2}$. These bands in our complexes appear along with strong bands of α - α' -dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline), since [VO(dipy)SO₄] and [VO(*o*-phen)SO₄] also exhibit strong bands in the region 1600 – 1630 cm^{-1} .

Taking all the infrared and other analytical results together it appears that in solid state vanadium(IV), in these complexes, is coordinated to oxo-oxygen, to two points of dipyrldyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) and to three points of the dibasic, tridentate Schiff base anion. Thus, effectively, the mixed complexes are six-coordinate in solid state.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectra of the complexes were examined in donor and non-donor solvents as also in solid state. The electronic spectra of majority of the complexes under discussion are not well resolved. Band I $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow e_{\pi}^*(d_{xz}, d_{yz})$ (Ballhausen-Gray¹⁰) appears as a broad one. It is not unlikely that this band covers the transition $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{yz}$. Furthermore, in most of the compounds it is not possible to identify unequivocally the second band *i.e.*, band II $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow b_1^*(dx^2-y^2)$. However, for the compound [VO(dipy)(Hynapan)] the resolution is better (Fig. 1) and the two bands can be

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of [VO(dipy)(Hynapan)] in different media :

- (A) Mull spectra
 - (B) Complex, $\cdot 005M$ in chloroform
 - (C) Complex, $\cdot 005M$ in pyridine.
- Optical density for (A) is arbitrary.

identified. Most complexes exhibit a band at ~ 25 – 20 kK in their mull spectra. This band very likely originates from charge transfer and intraligand transitions, their molar extinction coefficient in chloroform and pyridine being very high. In all the complexes the profile of the spectra, do not show any significant change from that in mull state to that in solvents (Table 3). This indicates that the same chromophore prevails in the three cases. Unfortunately, solvent-independent spectrum is no guarantee for a six-coordinate structure since it has been pointed out that an oxo-vanadium(IV) complex may be five-coordinate and may still refuse to accept any further sigma donation^{2,11}. Although electronic spectra of the present series of mixed chelates are not of a decisive nature, the infrared evidences favour six-coordinate structures for the complexes in solid state.

R E F E R E N C E S

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